

A Novel Approach for CNN-based Image Classification in Malaria Detection

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Abstract— Malaria, a life-threatening disease caused by Plasmodium parasites, remains a significant health challenge in many parts of the world. Rapid and accurate diagnosis is crucial to administer timely treatment and manage disease spread. Traditional diagnostic methods, like microscopic examination of blood slides, are labor-intensive and require skilled expertise. In this study, a novel approach using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for malaria cell classification is introduced. Digital images of blood samples are processed by the proposed model to identify and classify cells as infected or uninfected. Leveraging a dataset comprising thousands of labeled cell images, the CNN demonstrated superior performance compared to conventional methods, achieving an accuracy of 0.95. Our results underscore the potential of deep learning in enhancing diagnostic precision, reducing turnaround time, and offering a scalable solution, especially in resource-limited settings.

Keywords— Convolutional Neural Network , Conv2D, Deep learning, Keras, Machine Learning, Malaria detection, OpenCV, TensorFlow

I. INTRODUCTION

Malaria is a disease that's common in tropical countries and is mostly spread through the bites of female Anopheles mosquitoes that carry the infection. Traditionally doctors have relied on examining stained blood smears as the reliable way to diagnose malaria. However this method is time consuming, requires expertise and can be prone to error. Nowadays with the advancement of machine learning technology and the increasing availability of images there is a growing interest in automating the diagnostic process to improve speed, consistency and scalability.

In this context, CNNs[10], a subclass of deep learning models have emerged as a strong tool for image classification tasks. Specifically, for medical diagnostics, they carry the potential of high accuracy and quick processing, considerably assisting in illness monitoring and therapy. This study attempts to utilize the capabilities of CNNs to discern between infected and uninfected cell pictures, giving a contemporary approach to malaria detection.

We build a CNN model using the Keras API[11]. framework. This model helps us analyze images of blood smears taken under a microscope. By using layers, like Conv2D, MaxPool2D and Dense[10] this model learns patterns and characteristics associated with infected and uninfected cells. Additionally to overcome limitations posed

by datasets we make use of the ImageDataGenerator[10] to dynamically augment data ensuring that our model encounters representations of the information.

To monitor and improve the training process we employ techniques and tools such as Earlystopping[10], Adam optimizer[10] and binary cross entropy loss function. After the training is completed, we visualize the performance using accuracy and loss plots, which provide insights into how our model learned over time as well as its validation performance.

This initiative demonstrates the potential synergy between medical research and machine learning, where automated and exact malaria detection might become a reality, giving enormous advantages, particularly in resource-constrained areas.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Malaria is a major health concern in many regions of the globe that drive substantial research into improved diagnostic tools. One new technique blends the world of medical imaging with cutting-edge breakthroughs in deep learning. In particular, the CNN, a subtype of deep learning models recognized for its ability in image processing tasks, has shown substantial promise in the automated identification of malaria-infected cells.

Tania et al.[15] study aimed to develop a machine learning model to predict malaria based on bloodstream variables using Random Forest.

Rajaraman et al.[2] reported a new work on utilizing pre-trained CNNs for enhanced malaria parasite identification in thin blood smear pictures. Their solution, which employed CNNs as feature extractors, displayed extraordinary sensitivity and specificity, emphasizing the promise of deep learning in this area

Gopakumar et al.[3] pursued a new method by concentrating on blood smear pictures collected utilizing a custom-built slide scanner. Their technique, anchored on CNNs, highlighted the versatility of deep learning models in adapting to diverse data sources and reaffirmed the efficiency of CNNs in properly detecting malaria from those images

An article by Diaz et al.[4] not only dug into the measurement and categorization of infected erythrocytes but also demonstrated the combination of classic image analysis

approaches with machine learning. While this technique was not primarily based on CNNs, it gave essential insights that have guided future deep learning-focused projects

Poostchi et al.[5] provided an extensive analysis of various image analysis techniques, emphasizing the role of machine learning in detecting malaria. While offering a holistic overview, their research underlined the transformative potential of CNNs and their emerging role as a frontrunner in automated malaria detection.

In another work by Rajaraman et al.[6] the focus switched towards analyzing the performance of deep neural ensembles in malaria diagnosis. By using numerous CNN models and aggregating their results, the research demonstrated better robustness and accuracy, showing the advantages of ensemble approaches in clinical diagnosis.

Bibin et al.[1] ventured into Deep Belief Networks (DBN) for malaria parasite detection. While not a CNN in the traditional sense, the methodology adopted offered intriguing insights into the broader scope of deep learning beyond CNNs, signifying the breadth of methods available

III. MOTIVATION

Malaria, one of the oldest illnesses known to humans, continues to inflict a devastating impact on world health. As per the World Health Organization's figures, over half the world's population remains at danger of this illness, with hundreds of thousands dying from it each year. Primarily impacting the socio economically disadvantaged communities in tropical countries, its effect goes beyond merely health issues; it impedes economic growth, stresses healthcare systems, and widens the range of health disparities.

Amidst the persistent global challenge posed by malaria, traditional diagnostic methods have revealed their limitations in scalability and accuracy. In the era of artificial intelligence, this paper takes center stage.

Harnessing the exceptional capability of CNNs in image processing, this study seeks to improve malaria detection. By combining cutting-edge technology with an urgent health need, we seek to pave the path for a future where malaria testing is rapid, accurate, and accessible to everyone, linking contemporary innovation with revolutionary real-world effect.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This research utilized a systematic strategy to harness the potential of CNNs. Initial attempts involved gathering a strong dataset encompassing both infected and uninfected blood smear pictures, collected from reputable medical libraries.

After preprocessing and augmentation, ensuring the photos were of equal size and improving data diversity, we constructed a multi-layered CNN model appropriate for this classification job.

Model performance was gauged by measures including accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity, employing a split of the data into training, validation, and test sets.

Additionally, fine-tuning and optimization approaches were employed to strengthen the model's diagnostic capabilities, and the final findings were benchmarked against established diagnostic methods to assess comparative effectiveness.

The tasks that must be included are:

A. Data Collection

For the purposes of this study, pre-collected malaria cell images were used, sourced from the specified directory where these images are divided into two categories: "Uninfected" and "Parasitized".

B. Data Preprocessing

To provide a sense of the appearance of the raw cell photos, two example images one from each category were displayed.

To maintain uniformity while feeding the photos into the neural network, the images were then scaled to a standard size of 128x128 pixels.

In addition to rescaling pixel values between 0 and 1, an ImageDataGenerator was used to divide the dataset into training (80%) and validation (20%) subsets.

C. Machine Learning Model Selection

Due to CNN's superior performance in the image processing issues, it was chosen for this task.

There are several layers in CNN:

For feature extraction[14], three sets of convolutional layers are used, followed by max-pooling and dropout.

Two dense layers, a flattening layer, and a final layer with a sigmoid activation function[13] which denotes binary classification are present.

D. Training and Evaluation

'Binary_cross entropy[4]' was chosen as the loss function while compiling the model using the 'Adam' optimizer, making it appropriate for binary classification applications.

To avoid overfitting, an early stopping callback was used to stop training if the validation loss does not become better for two consecutive epochs.

The training terminated early at the 4th epoch because of the early stopping condition, even though the initial setup called for training for 20 epochs. Each of the seven epochs' outcomes was recorded, displaying the model's validation and training accuracy at each stage.

E. Final Prediction

When the model has trained through the fourth epoch, it is prepared to predict previously undetected cell pictures.

Using preprocessed picture data, predictions can be formed by applying the model's predict procedure.

In order to make sure the model is robust in producing accurate predictions given the early halting, it is essential to assess the model's performance on an independent test dataset or through further validation.

Plotting the losses and training and validation accuracies against the number of epochs provides information about how the model learns and can be used to assess the prediction reliability of the model.

V. BUILD MODEL

1. Importing required libraries

```
import tensorflow as tf
from tensorflow.keras import Sequential
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Conv2D,MaxPool2D,Dropout,Flatten,Dense,BatchNormalization
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
from tensorflow.keras.callbacks import EarlyStopping

import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

2. Importing the dataset

```
!kaggle datasets download -d iarunava/cell-images-for-detecting-malaria

Downloading cell-images-for-detecting-malaria.zip to /content
 98% 665M/675M [00:05<00:00, 51.3MB/s]
100% 675M/675M [00:05<00:00, 122MB/s]

!unzip cell-images-for-detecting-malaria.zip -d input
```

3. Displaying uninfected and infected cell images

```
import cv2

upic='./input/cell_images/Uninfected/C100P61ThinF_IMG_20150918_144104_cell_131.png'
apic='./input/cell_images/Parasitized/C100P61ThinF_IMG_20150918_144104_cell_164.png'
plt.figure(1, figsize = (15 , 7))
plt.subplot(1 , 2 , 1)
plt.imshow(cv2.imread(upic))
plt.title('Uninfected Cell')
plt.xticks([], plt.yticks([]))

plt.subplot(1 , 2 , 2)
plt.imshow(cv2.imread(apic))
plt.title('Infected Cell')
plt.xticks([], plt.yticks([]))

plt.show()
```

4. Dividing the dataset into testing and training set

```
datagen = ImageDataGenerator(rescale=1/255.0, validation_split=0.2)
```

5. Preparing train and test image generator

```
trainDatagen = datagen.flow_from_directory(directory='./input/cell_images/cell_images/',
target_size=(width,height),
class_mode = 'binary',
batch_size = 16,
subset='training')

Found 22048 images belonging to 2 classes.
```

```
valDatagen = datagen.flow_from_directory(directory='./input/cell_images/cell_images/',
target_size=(width,height),
class_mode = 'binary',
batch_size = 16,
subset='validation')
```

Found 5510 images belonging to 2 classes.

6. Preparing model

```
valDatagen = datagen.flow_from_directory(directory='./input/cell_images/cell_images/',
target_size=(width,height),
class_mode = 'binary',
batch_size = 16,
subset='validation')

model= Sequential()
model.add(Conv2D(16,(3,3),activation='relu',input_shape=(128,128,3)))
model.add(MaxPool2D(2,2))
model.add(Dropout(0.2))

model.add(Conv2D(32,(3,3),activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPool2D(2,2))
model.add(Dropout(0.3))

model.add(Conv2D(64,(3,3),activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPool2D(2,2))
model.add(Dropout(0.3))

model.add(Flatten())
model.add(Dense(64,activation='relu'))
model.add(Dropout(0.5))

model.add(Dense(1,activation='sigmoid'))

Found 5510 images belonging to 2 classes.

model.summary()
```

```
model.compile(optimizer='adam',loss='binary_crossentropy',metrics=['accuracy'])
```

```
early_stop = EarlyStopping(monitor='val_loss',patience=2)
```

```
history = model.fit_generator(generator = trainDatagen,
steps_per_epoch = len(trainDatagen),
epochs =20,
validation_data = valDatagen,
validation_steps=len(valDatagen),
callbacks=[early_stop])
```

```
Epoch 1/20
c:\python\input-23-54369da654e7>1: UserWarning: 'Model.fit_generator' is deprecated and will be removed in a future version. Please use 'Model.fit', which supports generator
history = model.fit_generator(generator = trainDatagen,
1378/1378 [=====] - 356s 257ms/step - loss: 0.6029 - accuracy: 0.6564 - val_loss: 0.3350 - val_accuracy: 0.8837
Epoch 2/20
1378/1378 [=====] - 353s 256ms/step - loss: 0.2053 - accuracy: 0.9331 - val_loss: 0.1718 - val_accuracy: 0.9347
Epoch 3/20
1378/1378 [=====] - 363s 263ms/step - loss: 0.1759 - accuracy: 0.9444 - val_loss: 0.1834 - val_accuracy: 0.9374
Epoch 4/20
1378/1378 [=====] - 369s 268ms/step - loss: 0.1631 - accuracy: 0.9498 - val_loss: 0.2386 - val_accuracy: 0.9347
```

7. Plots

```
def plotLearningCurve(history,epochs):
epochRange = range(1,epochs+1)
plt.plot(epochRange,history.history['accuracy'])
plt.plot(epochRange,history.history['val_accuracy'])
plt.title('Model Accuracy')
plt.xlabel('Epoch')
plt.ylabel('Accuracy')
plt.legend(['Train','Validation'],loc='upper left')
plt.show()

plt.plot(epochRange,history.history['loss'])
plt.plot(epochRange,history.history['val_loss'])
plt.title('Model Loss')
plt.xlabel('Epoch')
plt.ylabel('Loss')
plt.legend(['Train','Validation'],loc='upper left')
plt.show()
```

```
plotLearningCurve(history,4)
```

VI. IMPLEMENTATION

During the implementation phase we created a system using Streamlit app[14], for detecting malaria cells in images using a network model that had been trained. This system allows users to upload an image, which is then processed and resized to meet the models requirements. Once an image is received the system predicts whether it depicts a malaria infected cell or not. If there's uncertainty, in the prediction the user will be informed that the image might not be a representation of a malaria cell. Otherwise the result is shown by classifying the image as either infected or uninfected.

Fig1. Result displaying a cell infected with Malaria

Fig2. Result displaying uninfected cell

95% by the fourth epoch. This demonstrates its potential, as a diagnostic tool. The learning curves plotted during training and validation phases further support the performance of the model.

Fig3. Result displaying the uninfected and infected cell

Model: "sequential"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv2d (Conv2D)	(None, 126, 126, 16)	448
max_pooling2d (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 63, 63, 16)	0
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 63, 63, 16)	0
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 61, 61, 32)	4640
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 30, 30, 32)	0
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 30, 30, 32)	0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(None, 28, 28, 64)	18496
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 14, 14, 64)	0
dropout_2 (Dropout)	(None, 14, 14, 64)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 12544)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 64)	802880
dropout_3 (Dropout)	(None, 64)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 1)	65

Fig4. Result displaying model summary

VII. RESULT

The research primarily focuses on using CNN to distinguish between cell images infected with malaria and those that are uninfected. Data was obtained from a directory. Divided it into two categories: "Uninfected" and "Parasitized." These categories were further split into an 80% training set and a 20% validation set. The CNN model constructed for this purpose consists of three convolution layers, followed by max pooling layers to reduce dimensionality and dropout layers to prevent over fitting. After being trained for four epochs the model achieved levels of accuracy with the validation accuracy reaching

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10089720

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2023, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

Fig5. Result displaying model accuracy

VIII. CONCLUSION

Our research used CNN to categorize cell pictures into "infected" and "uninfected" categories in an effort to improve malaria detection methods.

The implemented CNN model demonstrated promising results in the preliminary stages, efficiently distinguishing between the two classes of cell images. Through the implementation of strategies such as data augmentation and early stopping the model demonstrated its ability to manage unbalanced datasets and avoid overfitting a critical aspect for practical use.

Although the primary focus of this study was on distinguishing between uninfected and infected cases there is a potential for research to expand its scope. This could

involve classifying stages of the malaria parasite or even identifying species of the parasite.

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